
EDUCATION TO THE RESCUE: TOWARDS ACHIEVING A SUSTAINABLE LEARNING AND TEACHING ENVIRONMENT IN TERTIARY EDUCATION FOR OPTIMAL RESULTS

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ABSTRACT

It is no longer news that the standard of education in Nigeria has drastically fallen. Different methods and approaches have been adopted severally to salvage the situation, but it has yielded no particular positive result. Bad teaching methods, poor reading habits, poverty, ill-equipped laboratories and libraries, are among the claims put by scholars that had caused the standard of education in Nigeria to dwindle. This paper examines the need to enhance the learning and teaching processes in tertiary education through balance student-Staff and student-student relationship to achieve a sustainable tertiary education system that will produce optimal results thereby salvaging the falling standard of education in Nigeria. The survey sample is the three Delta State-owned polytechnics and a campus of the Delta State University, in Delta State.

KEYWORDS: Tertiary Education, Student-Lecturer Relationship, Rescue, Results

INTRODUCTION

All over the world, tertiary education is singled-out as a centre of academic excellence. It is taken to be a centre where knowledge is being manufactured, shared and refined for the betterment of everybody in the society. As it were, tertiary institutions are expected to provide for the society, individuals who are balanced and refined in all aspects of human endeavour: academically, socially, morally, psychologically and otherwise.

The World Bank, as quoted in Micah et al (2006) opined that “ the norms, values, attitudes and ethics that tertiary institutions impart to students, either formally or informally, are the foundations of the social capital, necessary for cohesive culture; the bedrock of good governance and democratic political systems.”; while Esene (2009) notes that, “high education institutions, by virtue of their essence and programmes, have visions and missions that centre on knowledge generation, dissemination and application for sustainability and development.” In a related view Hannah (1998) stated that, tertiary institutions “... are enterprises that produce and distribute a public good, which is knowledge”

From the foregoing, it is evident that, knowledge is a product that is manufactured, processed and distributed by lecturers in the tertiary system of education. But, how can meaningful knowledge be passed into the society in an atmosphere devoid of mutual correlation and understanding between the lecturer “manufacturer/distributor” and the student “the primary consumer.”? For meaningful and yet, sustainable knowledge to be passed into the society, there must be good and cordial relationship between lecturers and their students. According to Ngara (1995), “... when there is appropriate lecturer-student relationship that facilitates both formal and informal interactions, the University (tertiary institutions) lecturers would transmit more than just knowledge and skills of his or her discipline.” For Marzino and Marzino, “the quality of staff and student relationship is the keystone for all other aspects of classroom management”; for such correlation “transcends the hand, but more importantly, it involves the mind, the heart and head” Ejiogu (1987).

The lecturer and his students as well as the students themselves need to have a good rapport within and outside the classroom. These relationships, especially that of student-student goes a long way in improving students’ intellectual capability, as they interact, discuss and study together, thereby helping to achieve the goals of tertiary education, which are enshrined in according Section 45 of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004), National Policy on Education (Revised).

Tertiary education community owes the society, the individual and itself a lot. It is however sad to note that, the custodians of this “betterment” of the society are yet to actually realise their “worth” due to their inability to establish a good academic relationship.

Lecturers are role models to their students and the society, and as such, any kind of relationship they enter into, with their students, will impact on the students and of course, the society, either negatively or positively. To this end, relationships between lecturers and students should be targeted at motivating them (the students) so as to impact positively on the larger society. As such, sexuality, favouritism, personal and tribal bias, and the like should be avoided in forming relationship between lecturers and students in the academic environment. It is on this backdrop, Micah et al (2006) cautioned that, "Students on their part should (also) perceive their relationship with lecturers as confident, meaningful and relevant to them." On his William (1996) opined that "interactions between students and campus characteristics that include interactions with their lecturers affect students' physical behaviour, their cognitive filtering of what they are experiencing and in the affective domain, their perceptions and attitudes toward campus environment."

Good relationship between lecturers and their students will go a long way in raising the dwindling standard of education in Nigeria; as bad relationship between them, will certainly endanger the academic and social life of the student; the educational system and the larger society. It is therefore the focus in this study to rescue the already fallen standard of education in Nigeria and other third world countries through an improved and cordial lecturer-student and student-student relationship to achieve a sustainable learning and teaching environment in tertiary education for optimal results and for the betterment of the society.

The findings in this study would be very relevant as they will help the lecturers to re-orientate themselves towards producing better products for the generality of the society. To the government and other concerned bodies, the findings will spur them into making policies that will guide against unethical relationships that exist between lecturers and students in tertiary institutions towards achieving the laudable goals of tertiary education. In the same vein, the following steps, though suggestive, if religiously adhered to, could also be useful in fostering relationship in tertiary education environment:

STEPS TO FOSTERING LECTURERS-STUDENTS RELATIONSHIP IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

- i. Know your students by their names and address them by their names. This will create a kind affinity that will encourage the students in participating in your class activities, since they will assume that you know them quite well, and that their absence would be too glaring to you.
- ii. Create time within the first two weeks of your class (mostly in the 1st semester), to individualize (not personalise) relationship with your students. This will no doubt make your students feel you are accessible, and hence, approachable.
- iii. Identify students with attention, and or, concentration problems; then direct your teaching on these set of students, by using them as your point of citing examples in your lectures, asking them questions or making them to read in class, if need be.
- iv. Initiate, new *Students'-Attention-Focused-Teaching-Methods* to be added to your habitual teaching style(s).
- v. Always work round the class especially when you are trying to explain 'salient points'. This will make you capture the attention of the students; assess their concentration and attention; and identify students who are active or not participating in the class activities.
- vi. Endeavour to simplify your teaching. Clear points that seem confusing, ambiguous and difficult to your students. By this, students would be more interested in your class. And of course, your class attendance will increase; your students would be more focused in class and your relationship with your students will continue to wax stronger.
- vii. Always make your class lively by being lively and active yourself.
- viii. Endeavour to research, study and prepare your lecturers before coming to the class. This will enable you to be lively yourself, be ready for unsuspecting questions and make you battle ready for the class.

Statement of the Problem

The quest for qualitative education and academic excellence has long being a thing of worry to stakeholders of the education sub-sector; hence the series of conferences, seminars, workshops and summits to checkmate its

standard. Adequate and qualitative manpower development is an obligation mostly to teaching staff of tertiary institutions as the “ivory tower of academic excellence”. But, how could this manpower, be developed without a conducive environment for providing and receiving it? The paper traced the inability of lecturers to form a working relationship between them and their students to be among other factors responsible for the continuous falling standard in the nation’s education system coupled with the lack and or, inability of the students themselves to organise or form reading clubs and partners. This is the main thrust in this article.

Aims and objectives of the study

The aims of this paper are:

- To contribute to an understanding of the nature of relationships in tertiary education communities and how the relationship can work to enhance teaching and student learning feat to salvage the already falling standard of education.
- To understand how the nature of the relationship might differ for teachers and their students as well as students and their co-students.
- To investigate the use of a socio-cultural perspective of learning to understand teaching and learning in higher education.

To achieve these aims the following objectives would be employed:

- To examine students’ the purposes of learning, how they learn and how good relationship with their lecturers impact on their learning;
- To examine lecturers’ perceptions of their purposes in teaching, their perceptions of student learning, and how their relationship with students impact on their teaching;
- To gather data on lecturers and student views about their relationships, observations of the relationships, and their development over time;
- To follow the progression of a group of students from year-one through final of their studies as well as asking lecturers about their perceptions and experience of teaching students at different levels;
- To plan and carry out the research proper, analyse the data, and reflect on how the data may further strengthen classroom relationship and raise the standard of education.

Research Question

This paper addresses the nature of relationship between academic staff and students as well as student-student in tertiary learning communities, and sought to understand, from the viewpoints of the participants, what it means to teach and learn in tertiary system of education. The paper particularly sought to use a socio-cultural approach to address the following questions:

- a. Does relationship exists between lecturers and students in tertiary institutions?
- b. Are you satisfied with the present relationship existing between lecturers and their students?
- c. Does the relationship between lecturers and their students does it include sex, favouritism, tribal and personal sentiments?
- d. Approachability/accessibility of lecturers does it enhance students’ participation and progress in class?
- e. The size of a class (population) does it constitute any problem to relationship building between students and lecturers; and among students?
- f. Student-student cordial relationship does it boost students’ academic progress?
- g. Interactive and reciprocal teaching methods, do they contribute to students’ active participation and progress in class?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design in this study is strictly the survey approach. The instruments for generating data were structured questions and interview. The population of the study consists of all the tertiary institutions in Delta State. The sampling method in selecting the four institutions is the simple random sampling method. 86 respondents were randomly selected and administered with questionnaires which were returned accordingly.

The questionnaire was keenly designed for respondents to produce YES or NO answers in accordance with the Gruttmann Scale Method. This was intended at facilitating straight- forward, accurate and timely completion of the questionnaires.

The instrument was validated by seasoned senior lecturers from both polytechnics and the Delta State University, as such it was reliable. Data from all the four institutions were compared to ascertain if the learning

and teaching processes in tertiary institutions could really be enhanced through a cordial working relationship between lecturers and students in order to produce results positively, thereby salvaging the falling standard of education in the country.

Research Question 1: Does relationship exists between lecturers and students in tertiary institutions?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	86	100%
NO	-	00%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

The above table shows 100% of the total respondents affirming the existence of relationship between lecturers and students in tertiary institutions. Thus, tertiary education environment permits relationship building between lecturers and their students.

Research Question 2: Are you satisfied with the present relationship existing between lecturers and their students?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	32	37.2%
NO	54	62.8%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

Though, relationship exists between lecturers and their students in tertiary institutions, it seems not to be satisfactory. This is evident from the 62.8% representing 54 of the total respondents expressing their dissatisfaction via their “NO” response, as to whether they are satisfied with the existing relationship between lecturers and students of tertiary institutions, contrary to the 37.2% satisfactory “YES” response. This is a strong indication that the relationship existing in the system is not certified adequate, and this needs improvement.

Research Question 3: Does the relationship between lecturers and their students does it include sex, favouritism, tribal and personal sentiments?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	-	00%
NO	86	100%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

The relationship existing between lecturers and their students in tertiary institutions is expected solely to boost students’ academic output. Sex, favouritism, personal and tribal sentiments should not feature as lecturer-student relationship. This is also the opinion of all the 86 respondents as they all disagree by responding “NO” to whether lecturer-student relationship should also include sex, favouritism, personal and tribal sentiments. The fact here is that, the classroom relationship or relationship that exists between lecturers and students is supposed to be formally and personal sentiment or interest free to enable all students feel equal and learn equal. By so doing, the lecturer would be able to assess the performances of the students in class.

Research Question 4: Approachability/accessibility of lecturers, does it enhance students’ participation and progress in class?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	81	94.2%
NO	05	5.8%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

The results from the above table indicates that when lecturers are accessible and approachable, students are encouraged to study as they can easily approach their lecturer(s) for clarification of difficult points on topics previously treated in class. In the same vein, they will be more enthusiastic to participate actively in class activities and of course, they will progress accordingly. This is obvious from the overwhelming 94.2% YES to the approachability and accessibility of lecturers as it encourages students' academic progress.

The fact is that, when lecturers provide consultation hours or create time in their offices to attend to students academic and other sensitive issues, it encourages the students, especially those with stage fright, who would not have had the enabling forum to speak or ask questions in the classroom, to have a one-to-one contact with the lecturers. This, in no doubt, will make the once "intimidated" students to regain confidence, feel the impact of the lecturer more and improve as well.

Research Question 5: The size of a class (population) does it constitute any problem to relationship building between students and lecturers; and among students?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	74	86%
NO	12	14%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

Class size constitutes a major problem to lecturer-students relationship building in tertiary institutions. This is indicated in the table above with 86% "YES" as against the 14% "NO". This is in consonance with a recent research by Micah et al (2006) that, "class size also featured as a factor influencing students' perception of lecturer-student relationship" and the World Bank (2000, 2002) as reported in Micah et al (2006) that "... Students faced difficult conditions of study which include overcrowded classes." In a nutshell, large class discourages relationship building, while small classes encourage quick relationship building, as students in smaller classes will find it easier and quicker to identify with one another, know themselves by name and interact with one another.

Research Question 6: Student-student cordial relationship does it boost students' academic progress?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	72	83.7%
NO	14	16.3%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

Students-students relationship is one of the enabling factors for students' quick understanding of a subject (course) that would ordinarily be difficult when earlier delivered by a lecturer in the class. This is because most students who are shy and have stage fright; and who may have disabilities, may find it difficult to express themselves in the classroom. But when they find themselves among a group of course-mates, or co-students, they can easily ask questions, request for clarifications and even contribute n group discussions. No wonder some quiet students are silently intelligent! This s also evident in the table above, where 83.7% of the total respondents affirming "YES" to student-student relationship as it relates to students' academic performance.

Research Question 7: Interactive and reciprocal teaching methods, do they contribute to students' active participation and progress in class?

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
YES	68	79%
NO	18	21%
TOTAL	86	100%

SOURCE: FIELD SURVEY, 2010

Though the lecturing method is the traditional teaching method in tertiary institutions, respondents still encourage the use of interactive and reciprocal teaching methods, as these methods compel the student to be

involved in the teaching-learning processes. This is affirmed from the table by the 79% “YES” as against the 21% “NO”.

Findings

The following were among the arguments that emerged from our analysis of data collected:

Relationships: One of the most outstanding arguments that surfaced from the case studies was the centrally vital roles relationships play in shaping the quality of teaching and learning experiences. Students and teachers in all the institutions remarked that developing “positive working relationships within the tertiary community were important.” This is applicable to both teacher–student and student–student relationships.

Teachers felt it important to get to know their students by name, address them as individuals, and show concern for student progress, both academically and otherwise. This was based on the notion that developing a relaxed teaching environment encourages student participation and performance in class activities.

A good teacher–student relationship was also perceived to have assisted teachers in accurately judging students’ progress. Students at all the institutions acknowledged the fundamental role that their working relationship with their lecturers played in shaping their learning experiences. This was apparent in factors such as approachability of the teacher, making classes more friendly and enjoyable, and motivating students to learn, etc. Students who saw their teachers as approachable and accessible were seen to be progressing faster than those without this relationship.

Student-Student Relationship: Students and teachers saw value in students developing relationships with one another. These relationships were seen to providing both moral and academic support in areas such as sharing ideas, books, and concerns about their learning, sharing of notes, and collaborating in their studies (group-reading). In situations where students were unable to develop these relationships early on in their course (first-year), they were seen to be at disarray and, as a result, both teachers and students felt it was essential for opportunities to be provided for these relationships to be developed early.

Size of the Class: A consistent theme across all case studies was the impact of class size on teaching and learning. There was obvious support for the benefits of small classes on student learning. Small classes were seen to promote teacher–student and student–student relationships, to encourage greater student involvement in learning processes and hence developing a sense of belonging in the learning environment. As noted above, relationships were reported to be tighter as students progressed from lower to higher levels as classes generally became smaller. As such, students progressed through their years of study, allowing greater individual interaction between students and teachers. Small class sizes encouraged students to participate more actively in class activities; attend classes more regularly as their absence would be noticed, and get help when they needed it.

Teaching Methods: Of all the available types of teaching and learning situations most commonly encountered in tertiary education (such as lectures, interactive classes, practical, tutorials, reciprocal teaching and field trips), interactive and reciprocal classes were the most highly rated by both students and teachers. Teachers saw interactive and reciprocal classes as avenues for better relationship development as the more informal a teacher is, the more he creates time for one-to-one conversation. Students found such classes interesting and more students-friendly; and both staff and students found these classes availing more and better chances for one-to-one discussion and relationship building. However, students value these aspects of the classroom; they opined that both theoretical (lecturing) and interactive aspects of teaching should be maintained.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research has shown that education is for the betterment of the generality of mankind. This education as we have seen can only come through the lecturer at the tertiary level of education to students who will go out to the outside world to sell the knowledge he or she has gained. However, knowledge as we can see from this study can only be passed in an atmosphere where there is mutual understanding and correlation between the lecturer and the student(s). In order to adequately manufacture, distribute and utilise this knowledge properly for the betterment of the society therefore, this paper hereby recommends the following:

i.) Lecturers should be friendly in classes and make themselves available in offices for students to learn and consult freely from; and to also interact and ask questions in order to gain “good” knowledge which they will use to impact on the society.

ii.) Both lecturers and students should understand the classroom and academic relationship to be purely for the purpose of imparting, gaining and disseminating knowledge for the benefit of themselves and for the larger society. As a result, their relationship should not be anchored on sexuality, favouritism and personal aggrandisement.

iii.) Since large classes constitute a problem to relationship building and the learning-teaching process in tertiary institutions, schools management, government and other stakeholders at this level of the education sub-sector should endeavour to build more classes and where possible should be reasonable in the yearly intake of new students to really check over-crowding in schools.

iv.) Students teaching themselves and, or discussing among themselves has been seen as another way of encouraging lonely and “shy” students to participate and even progress in class activities. Thus, students should initiate and form reading clubs, discussion classes and other self-motivating strategies to really encourage themselves and to make deficient students to have a sense of belonging in class.

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